

Financing biodiversity conservation through water tariffs: Nature-based Solutions for the Middle Brenta River Area (North-Eastern Italy)

Authors: Masiero, M.^a, Eusse-Villa, L.^a, Iacopino, S.^a, Amato, G.^b, Laghetto, G.^b, Cristofani, G.^c, Gatto, P.^a

Organisations: ^a University of Padova – Department of Land, Environment, Agriculture and Forestry (LEAF); ^b ETIFOR | valuing nature; ^c Consorzio di Bacino Brenta

Date: 24/06/2026

Keywords: Nature-Based Solutions (NbS), biodiversity, financial mechanisms, ecosystem management, land management, water tariffs

Executive summary

Biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation require new financial mechanisms to support conservation, restoration, and long-term ecosystem management. This report presents a case study from the middle Brenta River area in North-Eastern Italy, where Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are assessed as a potential pathway for financing biodiversity restoration and the provision of co-benefits through water tariffs.

The study area is strategically important because it supplies drinking water to approximately 1.5 million people and overlaps with the Natura 2000 site “*Grave e Zone umide della Brenta*”, i.e. Gravel beds and wetlands of the Brenta river (IT3260018). Despite its ecological and hydrological importance, the area is affected by intensive agriculture, groundwater depletion, habitat fragmentation, gravel mining, pressure by recreational activities, and limited integrated governance.

The study assesses five alternative NbS scenarios against a baseline scenario representing current land-use and management conditions. The selected NbS are conservation agriculture, constructed wetlands, and forest infiltration areas, implemented either as stand-alone interventions or in blended configurations. The scenarios are evaluated against three ecosystem service (ES) indicators: water infiltration, carbon sequestration, and habitat quality. A cost-effectiveness assessment is also carried out to compare the relative efficiency of each intervention.

The results indicate that forest infiltration areas perform best for groundwater recharge and carbon sequestration, while constructed wetlands provide the strongest habitat-quality improvement. However, blended NbS scenarios offer the most balanced overall performance by combining multiple benefits at moderate cost. The findings support establishing an environmental fund financed through water tariffs, creating a dedicated mechanism to channel financial resources into biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration.

1. Background

The global biodiversity crisis has created an urgent need for financing instruments that can mobilize resources beyond conventional public funding. Existing estimates suggest that hundreds of billions of euros are needed annually to reverse biodiversity decline, while current public and private financing remains insufficient (UNEP, 2026). In Europe, this challenge is addressed through policy frameworks such as the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy, and the Nature Restoration Law (European Commission, 2019; European Union, 2024).

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are increasingly recognized as cost-effective interventions that can address societal challenges while delivering benefits for biodiversity, climate mitigation, and ecosystem resilience (UNEP, 2026). However, their implementation is often constrained by fragmented governance, uncertainty around ecological benefits, and limited access to stable funding streams (Maes & Jacobs, 2017; Nesshöver et al., 2017; Sarabi et al., 2020).

This report focuses on an innovative biodiversity-finance model based on the integration of ecosystem services (ES) benefits into water-resource management. Specifically, it examines whether water tariffs can contribute to a dedicated environmental fund for mitigation and compensation measures linked to the Integrated Water Service. This approach has particular relevance for areas where water extraction, habitat protection, and biodiversity conservation intersect.

The case study is located in the middle section of the Brenta River in Veneto, North-Eastern Italy. The area covers approximately 1,524 hectares and includes a well field that supplies approximately 36.8 million cubic meters of drinking water annually, serving 1.5 million people. Around 45% of the area falls within the Natura 2000 network – named as “Grave e Zone umide della Brenta”, i.e. Gravel beds and wetlands of the Brenta river (IT3260018) – being home to more than 70 fauna and flora species and hosting five relevant habitats, including a priority one i.e. Alluvial forests with Alder and Ash. Despite being a hotspot for both water and biodiversity, the area is densely populated and challenged by several threats, such as intensive agriculture (annual crop and livestock farming), tap water extraction and water table lowering, mining activities (gravel extraction from the riverbed), habitat fragmentation and lack of ecological connectivity, pressure due to intense recreation activities. In more general terms, poor governance and lack of an integrated management.

2. Methodological approach

The analysis compares the current land-use and management baseline with five alternative NbS scenarios. The NbS were selected through stakeholder consultations and expert input developed within the [Life Brenta 2030 Project](#) context. Stakeholders included public authorities, academia, water service providers, private-sector representatives, and farmers' associations.

Three categories of NbS were considered:

1. **Conservation agriculture**, aimed at improving agricultural sustainability and reducing nutrient pressure.
2. **Constructed wetlands**, aimed at improving water quality and strengthening habitat conditions.
3. **Forest infiltration areas**, aimed at increasing groundwater recharge and enhancing carbon sequestration.

Suitability maps were developed for each NbS type using land-use data, environmental criteria, hydrological conditions, land ownership, proximity to watercourses, and agricultural pressure. These maps were used to identify where each intervention could be implemented most effectively. Table 1 presents the assessed scenarios, while Table 2 shows the indicators used to assess the ES.

Table 1. Scenarios assessed.

Scenario	Description
Baseline (BAS)	Current land use and management practices
Conservation agriculture (CON)	Conservation agriculture implemented in all suitable areas
Constructed wetlands (WET)	Constructed wetlands implemented in all suitable areas
Forest Infiltration Areas (FIA)	Forest infiltration areas implemented in all suitable areas
Mixed scenario 1 (MIX1)	Blended scenario prioritizing forest infiltration areas, then wetlands, then conservation agriculture
Mixed scenario 2 (MIX2)	Blended scenario prioritizing wetlands, then forest infiltration areas, then conservation agriculture

Table 2. ES assessment

Indicator	Purpose
Water infiltration	Proxy for groundwater recharge and water-resource support
Carbon sequestration	Proxy for climate-mitigation benefits
Habitat quality	Proxy for biodiversity conservation and habitat improvement

The Natura Capital Project InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs) spatially explicit model suite was used to assess ES outcomes, while QGIS and R were used for spatial processing, index calculation, and comparison across scenarios.

A cost-effectiveness analysis was then conducted over a 30-year period using a 3% discount rate.

3. Key results

3.1. Water infiltration

The forest infiltration area scenario yielded the greatest improvement in water infiltration, with an additional 30,100 m³ of retained water, representing an increase of approximately 8% compared with the baseline.

The MIX1 blended scenario also performed strongly, increasing infiltration by 25,633 m³, equivalent to a 6.8% improvement. Conservation agriculture produced a smaller positive effect, with an increase of 7,533 m³, or approximately 2%.

Constructed wetlands reduced water infiltration by 90,274 m³, corresponding to a 23.9% decrease compared with the baseline. MIX2 showed a smaller reduction of 1,681 m³, or 0.4%.

3.2. Carbon sequestration

All NbS scenarios increased carbon sequestration relative to the baseline. The greatest improvements were observed in the forest infiltration area and the MIX1 blended scenarios.

The baseline stored approximately 58,066 tons of CO₂. The forest infiltration area scenario increased this value to 109,155 tons of CO₂, representing an improvement of approximately 88%. MIX1 performed similarly, reaching 109,357 tons of CO₂, equivalent to an 88.3% increase.

Constructed wetlands also improved carbon sequestration, reaching 69,633 tons of CO₂, or around 19.9% above baseline. Conservation agriculture showed the smallest increase, reaching 59,723 tons of CO₂, or 2.85% above baseline.

3.3. Habitat quality

All alternative scenarios improved habitat quality relative to the baseline. Constructed wetlands achieved the highest habitat-quality score, increasing the index from 0.387 to 0.459, an 18.6% increase. MIX1 followed closely with a habitat-quality index of 0.456, representing a 17.8% improvement.

Forest infiltration areas also performed well, reaching an index of 0.453, or 17.1% above baseline. MIX2 achieved a 15.2% increase, while conservation agriculture showed a smaller improvement of approximately 1%.

4. Cost-effectiveness findings

The cost-effectiveness analysis shows important trade-offs between ecological performance and implementation cost. Conservation agriculture was the most cost-efficient option, with estimated annual costs of 0.29 EUR per m³ of infiltrated water and 1.87 EUR per ton of sequestered CO₂. However, its ecological effectiveness was relatively limited, thus limiting its practical implementation.

Constructed wetlands were the most expensive option, with estimated costs of 14.73 EUR per m³ of infiltrated water and 60.92 EUR per ton of CO₂ sequestered. Although wetlands performed strongly for habitat quality, they were less cost-effective for water infiltration and carbon sequestration.

Forest infiltration areas presented moderate costs, estimated at 4.54 EUR per m³ of infiltrated water and 17.00 EUR per ton of CO₂. They performed particularly well for groundwater recharge and carbon sequestration.

The blended scenarios presented intermediate cost-effectiveness values. MIX1 was the most balanced option, with costs of 6.91 EUR per m³ of infiltrated water and 25.54 EUR per ton of CO₂. This scenario combined strong ES performance with moderate implementation costs.

5. Policy implications

The results can support the creation of an environmental fund financed through water tariffs. Building on the “user pays” principle set by the Water Framework Directive, such a mechanism would help internalize environmental and resource costs associated with water-service provision and channel financial resources toward NbS that generate measurable ecosystem-service benefits.

This model is relevant to biodiversity finance because it links local environmental pressures, water resource management, and conservation funding. It also aligns with European policy priorities, including the Water Framework Directive, the Water Resilience Strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy, and the Nature Restoration Law.

The proposed mechanism can be interpreted as a quasi-Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) model, where water users contribute to interventions that protect the ecosystems supporting water provision. By integrating NbS into tariff-based financing, the model provides a stable, long-term funding stream for biodiversity conservation.

The findings also indicate that single-intervention strategies may not be sufficient. Forest infiltration areas and constructed wetlands each perform well for single objectives but might generate some trade-offs among ES. For example, results suggest that constructed wetlands may provide important biodiversity benefits but are less effective as a stand-alone solution when groundwater recharge is a priority. On the contrary, blended NbS portfolios provide a better balance across water, carbon, and biodiversity indicators. This is important for decision-makers seeking to maximize ecological benefits while maintaining financial feasibility.

6. Conclusions

This report demonstrates that NbS can support biodiversity conservation, water resource management, and climate mitigation in the middle section of the Brenta River. The analysis shows that forest infiltration areas are particularly effective for groundwater recharge and carbon sequestration, while constructed wetlands are most effective for habitat quality. However, blended NbS scenarios offer the most balanced performance. This makes it a promising option for biodiversity-finance strategies based on water tariffs.

Results provide technical and scientific ground for setting-up an environmental fund which represents an innovative mechanism for linking ES benefits to water-service financing. It can support long-term investment in biodiversity conservation and restoration while aligning with European Union policy frameworks and local stakeholder priorities.

Further research should include opportunity-cost assessment, additional valuation of habitat-quality improvements, and analysis of citizens' willingness to pay through water bills. These steps would strengthen the financial and social feasibility of the proposed mechanism and support its replication in other water-dependent Natura 2000 and riverine landscapes.

References

- European Commission. (2019). *The European Green Deal*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640>.
- European Union. (2024). *The EU Nature Restoration Law*. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/nature-restoration-law_en.
- Maes, J., & Jacobs, S. (2017). Nature-based solutions for Europe's sustainable development. *Conservation Letters*, 10(1), 121–124.
- Nesshöver, C., Assmuth, T., Irvine, K. N., Rusch, G. M., Waylen, K. A., Delbaere, B., Haase, D., Jones-Walters, L., Keune, H., & Kovacs, E. (2017). The science, policy and practice of nature-based solutions: An interdisciplinary perspective. *Science of the Total Environment*, 579, 1215–1227.
- Sarabi, S., Han, Q., Romme, A. G. L., de Vries, B., Valkenburg, R., & den Ouden, E. (2020). Uptake and implementation of Nature-Based Solutions: An analysis of barriers using Interpretive Structural Modeling. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 270, 110749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2020.110749>.
- UNEP (2026). *State of Finance for Nature 2026: Nature in the Red: Powering the Trillion Dollar Nature Transition Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822/49119>.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.